

USE OF NEWS DISCOURSE SEMANTICS OF PRIMITIVES IN
LINGUOCULTUROLOGICAL RESEARCH**Jawmitbaeva Perizat Karamatdinovna**Assistant teacher of Karakalpak Institute of
Agriculture and agro technology**Abstract**

This article analyzes different points of view on such concept as the Internet discourse and its characteristics. The problem of the lack of a unified approach to the study of the phenomenon of the Internet discourse is actualized. The author also draws attention to the fact that the Internet discourse as a category associated with the functioning of implicit information itself predetermines the difficulties of perception, decoding and interpretation of the meaning of the language of the Internet communication. As a result of the analysis, the author concludes that there is a need for a comprehensive approach to the study of this issue, in the aspect of the rapid development of communication technologies in general and the Internet communication in particular, including that need in terms of cross-language comparison.

Key words: discourse, implication, Internet discourse, communicant, polycode, expressive and emotional media, mass media, modern newspaper discourse.

The inexpressible is studied in newspaper discourse, since in it emotional and expressive expression is very often transmitted through the category of inexpressibility. In Uzbek linguistics, the interest in studying the features of the newspaper style still relevant. It is shown that the most developed expressive and emotional means and techniques of newspaper texts are the functioning of tropes and figures of speech, as well as the evaluation of newspaper discourse. Current problems review in the study of the semantics of the inexpressible has shown that there is not a single study devoted to the investigation of the inexpressible in newspaper discourse. Researches on the

study of the nature of the inexpressible as illustrative material use primarily artistic texts and works of folklore. As for newspaper discourse texts, the theory and practice of their linguistic analysis have not been studied from the point of view of using the semantics of the inexpressible. The material for further research will be a modern newspaper discourse focused on the presentation of the semantics of the inexpressible. The article defines the current prospects for the study of the semantics of the inexpressible in newspaper discourse, which allows us to determine the practical significance of this work in line with new approaches to the study of the semantics of the inexpressible in newspaper discourse. We believe that the study of semantic and functional properties of the inexpressible in newspaper discourse is an urgent scientific task.

There is not a single special study devoted to the study of the semantics of the inexpressible in newspaper discourse. Scientific works on the study of the nature of the inexpressible are based primarily on artistic texts as illustrative material. As for the texts of newspaper discourse, the theory and practice of their linguistic analysis has not been studied from the point of view of using the semantics of the inexpressible. This determines the relevance of the topic we have chosen. We believe that this study is necessary, since the semantics of the inexpressible, being a conceptual category, has the means of transmission in newspaper discourse. The research material will be a modern newspaper discourse focused on the presentation of the semantics of the inexpressible. We will need to determine the means of language, speech and other semiotic systems of newspaper discourse; the conditions under which the use of the inexpressible in newspaper discourse is possible; genres of newspaper discourse in which the use of the inexpressible is allowed; situations of manifestation of the semantics of the inexpressible in newspaper texts. Today, in all branches of science and economics, is being formed as a time of innovative technologies, and in parallel with the rapid development of technologies, society itself and the natural need of humanity for new, more convenient communication channels are growing. The technical means that entered our everyday life at the turn of the century contribute to the formation and development of new cultural forms in the field of public relations,

and communication in the virtual space becomes an indispensable part of reality. In the last decade, many linguists have distinguished communication on the Internet as a special kind of discourse and discursive practice. It can be stated that discourse in communicative linguistics today is the main concept. In linguistics, there are several approaches to the interpretation and understanding of this term. Dutch linguist Theun van Dijk reveals the term discourse as a communicative act taking place in a specific social, cultural, temporal and spatial context, the participants of which are two people. The concept of "discourse" in linguistics is perceived as synonymous with the concepts of "conversation" and "text". For example, in the modern explanatory dictionary of the Russian language edited by T.F. Efremova, the concept of "discourse" is revealed as "conversation, conversation as an object of linguistic research" [6]. It should be noted that Internet discourse means communication not only on Internet sites (on pages of social networks, forums and other platforms for communication), but also through specialized applications, including on the platform of mobile devices (mobile applications of social networks, instant messaging tools - messengers, etc.), connected to the Internet [4]. So, speaking about Internet discourse, we mean communication on Internet sites and in numerous applications (including mobile ones) on the vast global network. The endless possibilities of the Internet allow you to communicate both personality-oriented (personal correspondence) and status-oriented (communication in various chat rooms, conversations of communities created on various topics and problems). The concept of "correspondence" with the development of Internet capabilities loses its true content and turns into a term nominating the process of sending and receiving messages of different content between interlocutors, i.e. correspondence is the process of exchanging messages. This is due to the fact that today, in the process of communication via the Internet, it is possible to send not only written text, but also audio, video, photos or combined, so-called polycode messages.

It is necessary to keep in mind another feature of Internet communication based on communication in actual and virtual environments. This makes up the so-called discursive space, which in turn is a set of communicative units (communicants), i.e. different in volume, content, meaning, completed and incomplete, implicit and explicit,

dialogic and monological, oral, written, etc. statements [7]. But still, there is no single point of view among linguists on such a phenomenon of modernity as Internet discourse, and this phenomenon must be considered the result of the rapid development of computer, as a consequence, communication technologies and the global Internet as a whole, when a person from almost anywhere in the world can go online and start communicating. According to E.N. Galichkina, Internet communication has all the characteristics that other types of communication have. Thus, Internet communication contains the characteristics of mass, intrapersonal and group communication. Paying attention to the time factor, it should be noted that here we mean the duration of the communicative process: communication in the vastness of the global network can be both brief and unlimited in time. From the point of view of the information transmission channel and its perception, Internet communication is divided into actual (communication with well-known interlocutors) and virtual (anonymous communication) [4]. Researcher E.N. Galichkina identifies the concept of "Internet discourse" primarily with communication affecting certain life situations and problems (for example, medicine, politics, sports, economic activity, etc.), where online discussion of various issues, polemics of users (as already mentioned, in most cases completely unfamiliar) is seen as a way of implementing Internet discourse with each other), defending their vision of the situation [4]. Nevertheless, the individualizing feature of Internet communication is that, firstly, it is carried out using communication devices connected to the global network (personal computers, laptops, tablet computers, mobile devices, smart watches and other various gadgets), secondly, this communication is increasingly turning into a symbiosis of various ways transmission of information from one user to another (written text, audio and video messages, graphic images, including the use of INTERNET DISCOURSE AS an object of linguistic research) PROBLEMS OF ORIENTAL STUDIES. 2020/1 (87) emoticons). In this situation, as already mentioned above, the issue of a polycode text is being updated. Another feature of the Internet language, as noted by A.E. Voiskunsky, is that the written form of speech is stylistically as close as possible to the informal oral colloquial style [2], especially in the part concerning the informal correspondence of

users. Speaking about the interpretation of Internet discourse by A.E. Voiskunsky, it is necessary to pay attention to such general discursive signs as: 1) dynamism and processality; 2) communication; 3) personification; 4) situational conditionality; 5) connotativity; 6) social and cultural labeling [2]. According to A.E. Voiskunsky, internet discourse is a system characterized by these features [2]. It is important to note that Internet discourse, like any kind of discourse, is conditioned by the presence of genres (e-mail – e-mail, various chats, blogs, forums, social networks, diaries, instant messaging applications – messengers), which may reflect general and specific properties. One of the specific properties of the Internet discourse N.A. Akhrenova calls a lexical subsystem that has certain linguistic features and has socio-cultural characteristics, for example, the use of familiar vocabulary by a certain group of people (age, interests, professional, etc.) creates the effect of ease, trust and helps to establish contact, for some users this approach can turn complex concepts into simple ones [1].

As for the chronology of Internet discourse, it is to some extent limited by technical capabilities (this is the presence or absence of an Internet connection), and, of course, by the human factor (the presence or absence of a user on-line). However, since the Internet is an artificially created communicative field, Internet discourse should be devoid of all temporal and spatial boundaries. Today, the virtual space appears to us in the form of a multitude of network entities, where all participants of the Internet discourse accumulate - chats, forums, social networks, messengers, etc. [7].

In turn, the user's involvement in Internet discourse can be defined as passive (searching for the necessary information and its "consumption") or active (initiating topics and actively participating in their discussion, defending their point of view). Researcher A.A. Selyutin also notes the different degree of user involvement in Internet discourse. By passivity, he means a form of communication where the user only receives information without providing anything in return. The purpose of such a user in Internet communication is to search for and receive information. Such users remain out of sight of other participants of the communicative process on the Internet, their image and "traces" of their stay are not recorded in Internet communication, meanwhile

the consequences of the stay of an active communicant are noticeable, are visible to other users and create a certain communicative image. AA Selyutin identifies four goals of an active user in the process of Internet communication: - the exchange of information (not only unrealized, but also the exchange of audio and video files, graphic images and other digital data of various kinds); – the creation and strengthening of contacts (the communicator, depending on his intention, can look for contacts related to his biography, professional activity, sphere of interests and inclinations, religious and moral values); – self-realization (AA Selyutin characterizes this point as: "Increasing personal rating due to their knowledge or actions, as well as as a consequence of the degree of benefit of this communicant for the network community") [8]; – communication for the purpose of entertainment, which, according to many linguists, is one of the main points in Internet communication.

In many studies, scientists do not identify the concepts of "discourse", "communication" and "communication" and define discourse as a complex text system, dialogical and interactive in nature and determined by extra linguistic socio-cultural factors. Moreover, the Internet discourse as a whole can be interpreted as a specific one that combines other types of discourses and is the main platform for accessing them. Virtual discourse is characterized mainly by the nature of those devices, including communicative ones (their capabilities are expanding daily), which provide a communication channel via the global Internet. The so-called computer discourse today appears to be one of the numerous types of Internet discourse and is characterized only by the use of a stationary, personal computer, as well as the use of a mobile phone could give rise to a mobile type of Internet discourse.

The main goal of Internet communication is closely intertwined with the goals of communication in general and has its own characteristics inherent only in the digital world. Therefore, having an artificial pedigree, Internet discourse can serve not just as one of the communication channels of the modern world, such as a telephone or fax, but claims to become a new, completely different level of platform for communication and self-realization. On this platform, communicants do not meet face to face (although the technological capabilities for making a video call are available in almost all

applications), but even without this there is a direct and multifaceted communicative impact. Thanks to the capabilities of modern communication technology, Internet discourse acquires a huge number of distinctive features, while maintaining the characteristics characteristic of the discourse as a whole. The vocabulary of Internet discourse has stable features of the written and oral varieties of the language, and also actively incorporates some features of technical jargon, common vocabulary and is formed according to the principles of the formation of informal vocabulary, i.e. uncontrolled, irregular, and, as a result, has a high degree of implicitness. This fact is caused, among other things, by the specifics of the communicative field, the peculiarities of the active use of diverse vocabulary, as well as factors based on the level of social and cultural development of a particular society, where the Internet as a whole arises and spreads. At the same time, it should be noted that the modern approach to the study of Internet discourse, despite its relevance, remains still insufficiently developed, since the language of Internet communication, as a living and complex organism, is constantly evolving along with the technological progress of modernity.

In addition, Internet discourse as a category associated with the functioning of implicit information, in itself determines the difficulties of perception, decoding and interpretation of the meaning of the language of Internet communication. Due to such a special status of vocabulary on the Internet, the indisputable importance of its research and the enormous interest for scientists, a comprehensive approach to its study is necessary, including elements of different scientific approaches: linguistic, literary, cultural, ethnographic, including in terms of interlanguage comparison.

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